

Phytochemical Studies on the Genus *Crotalaria*: Part VIII. Chemical Constituents of *Crotalaria mysorensis* Roth

R. S. Sawhney and C. K. Atal

In continuation to our systematic study of Indian *Crotalaria* we were interested to examine the seeds of *Crotalaria mysorensis*. The plant¹ is an annual herb which is common throughout India. For the present studies the seeds were collected from Akhnoor (Jammu). In this communication we report the isolation of β -sitosterol, scopoletin and the pyrrolizidine diester, monocrotaline.

Powdered material assayed by the method of Culvenor and Smith² was found to contain tertiary bases 0.09% and its N-oxides 0.01%.

The powdered seeds (1.6 kg) were extracted with petroleum ether for 32 hr. The petrol extract on concentration yielded solid material which on further recrystallisation from alcohol was identified as β -sitosterol. The defatted seeds were further extracted with alcohol, solvent distilled off under reduced pressure and residue treated with 5% sulphuric acid and reduced with zinc dust. The solution was filtered and the filtrate extracted with petroleum ether and subsequently with chloroform. The chloroform extractions on removal of solvent yielded pale yellow crystals (90 mg) which after recrystallisation from methanol melted at 203-204°, TLC (fluorescent R_f 0.71 in methanol), paper chromatography (R_f 0.7 in upper layer of butanol saturated with equal volume of 5% acetic acid), R_T 5.5 min. (column packed with Gas Chrom P bearing 4% SE 30, 200°, 50 ml N_2 /min.). (Found C, 61.28, H, 4.20, Calc. for $C_{28}H_{48}O_4$, C, 62.50 and H, 4.20%). Its molecular weight 192 was derived from mass spectrum. The mass spectral fragmentation of the compound showed fragmentations identical with those of scopoletin³ (6-methoxy-7-hydroxy coumarin). In the mass spectrum of the compound, very minor peaks due to isomer³ of scopoletin have also been observed. The NMR spectrum ($CDCl_3$) of the compound shows one pair of doublets, one at δ 6.23 (1H) and 7.58 (1H), $J=9.5$ c/s, corresponding to protons at H_3 and H_4 of scopoletin. Two singlets at δ 6.83 (1H) and 6.90 (1H) correspond to protons at H_2 and H_5 of scopoletin; a singlet at δ 3.93 (3H) can be assigned to aromatic methoxy group of scopoletin. Presence of -OH group was confirmed by D_2O exchange in the mass spectrum.

IR of the compound was superimposable to that of scopoletin. The compound in sodium hydroxide absorbs at 242 and 400 $m\mu$ which further confirms it to be scopoletin⁴. To our knowledge this is the first report of isolation of a coumarin from the genus *Crotalaria*.

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2. C. C. J. Culvenor and L. W. Smith, *Australian J. Chem.*, 1955, **8**, 556.
3. R. T. Aplin and C. B. Page, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 2593.
4. F. M. Dean, Brian Parton, Nongyow Somvichien and D. A. H. Taylor, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967, **23**, 2147.

The acidic solution was now basified with ammonia and extracted with chloroform. On concentration and keeping at room temperature for a day, it deposited pale yellow needles (1.2 g.) which after recrystallisation from alcohol gave colourless crystalline material m.p. 200-201°, TLC (R_f 0.53 in chloroform-methanol ammonia 85:14:1) paper chromatography (R_f 0.38 in upper layer of n-butanol saturated with equal volume of 5% acetic acid), R_T 7.4 min. (210°, 60 ml N_2 /min.) has (α_D^{18} -16.2 (C, 1.2%, alcohol). (Found C, 58.80; H, 7.0; N, 4.4; 0.28.5; Calc. for $C_{16}H_{23}NO_6$, C, 59.0; H, 7.1; N, 4.3 and 0.29.5%). It readily formed picrate m.p. (237-38°) (Found: C, 48.0; H, 4.82; N, 10.0; Calc. for $C_{16}H_{23}O_6N \cdot C_6H_3N_3O_7$, C, 47.6, H, 4.7 and N, 10.1%).

Above mentioned data and Mass, NMR and IR spectra were found identical to those of authentic monocrotaline.

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REGIONAL RESEARCH LABORATORY,
(COUNCIL OF SCIENTIFIC & INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH),
JAMMU.

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